

WEAKLY IRREDUCIBLE UP-FILTERS IN MEET-COMMUTATIVE UP-ALGEBRAS

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ABSTRACT. The concept of meet-commutative UP-algebras was introduced in 2016 by Sawika et al. Muhiuddin et al. introduced in 2021 the concept of prime UP-filter (of the first kind) and irreducible UP-filter in meet-commutative UP-algebras. Also, it has been shown that any prime UP-filter in such algebras is irreducible. In this paper, we introduce the concept of weakly irreducible UP-filters in such algebras and show that the prime UP-filter is between this and the irreducible UP-filter. Also, we show the possibility that each irreducible UP-filter is a weakly irreducible UP-filter.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of KU-algebras was introduced in 2009 by C. Prabpayak and U. Leerawat in the article [9]. In 2017, A. Iampan [3] introduced the concept of UP-algebras as a generalization of KU-algebras. In [17], Somjanta et al. introduced the notion of filters in this class of algebras. Jun and Iampan then introduced and analyzed several classes of filters in UP-algebras such as implicative, comparative and shift UP-filters (see, for example, [4, 5, 6]). Romano also took part in the analysis of filter types in such algebras as proper UP-filter [11] and (with Y. B. Jun) weak implicative UP-filter [14].

The concept of meet-commutative UP-algebras was introduced in article [15] by Sawika et al. In such algebras, Muhiuddin et al. introduced the concepts of prime (of the first kind) and irreducible UP-filters [8]. In that paper it is also shown that any prime UP-filter in meet-commutative UP-algebra is an irreducible UP-filter. Continuing to develop the ideas introduced in the mentioned paper [8], Romano introduced the concepts of prime UP-filters of the second [12] and the third kind [13]. This seems to justify the author's interest in studying the properties of UP-algebras in which the property of meet-commutativity is present.

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A UP-filter F of a meet-commutative UP-algebra A is said to be an *irreducible UP-filter* of A if for any UP-filters S and T of A the following implication holds

$$F = S \cap T \implies (S = F \vee T = F).$$

In an effort to better understand the properties of this class of logical algebras, the author analyzed the possibility of weakening the hypothesis in the previous implication. The consequence of the $S \cap T \subseteq F$ option is considered. As a consequence of this choose, a new class of UP-filters in meet-commutative UP-algebras was obtained.

In this paper, the author introduces the concept of weakly irreducible UP-filters in meet-commutative UP-algebras (Definition 4.1), gave one important characterization of such UP-filter (Theorem 4.1) and connects it with irreducible (Theorem 4.3 and Theorem 4.4) and prime UP-filters (Theorem 4.2).

2. PRELIMINARIES

This section introduces the concepts and processes with them that will be used in the main section.

2.1. UP-algebras. In this subsection, taking from the literature, we will repeat the logical environment of interest for this research.

An algebra $A = (A, \cdot, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is called a *UP-algebra* (see [3]) if it satisfies the following axioms:

- (UP-1) $(\forall x, y, z \in A)((y \cdot z) \cdot ((x \cdot y) \cdot (x \cdot z)) = 0)$,
- (UP-2) $(\forall x \in A)(0 \cdot x = x)$,
- (UP-3) $(\forall x \in A)(x \cdot 0 = 0)$,
- (UP-4) $(\forall x, y \in A)((x \cdot y = 0 \wedge y \cdot x = 0) \implies x = y)$.

Example 2.1. ([3], Example 1.6) Let $A = \{0, a, b, c\}$ and operations ‘ \cdot ’ defined on A as follows:

\cdot	0	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c
a	0	0	0	0
b	0	a	0	c
c	0	a	b	0

Then $A = (A, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra where.

In a UP-algebra, the order relation ‘ \leq ’ is defined as follows

$$(\forall x, y \in A)(x \leq y \iff x \cdot y = 0).$$

2.2. UP-filters. A subset F of a UP-algebra A is called a *UP-filter* of A (see [17]) if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (F-1) $0 \in F$,
- (F-2) $(\forall x, y \in A)((x \in F \wedge x \cdot y \in F) \implies y \in F)$.

It is clear that every UP-filter F of a UP-algebra A satisfies:

- (1) $(\forall x, y \in A)((x \in F \wedge x \leq y) \implies y \in F)$.

The family of all UP-filters of a UP-algebra A is denoted by $\mathfrak{F}(A)$. It is easy to verify that the intersection of UP-filters of a UP-algebra A is also a UP-filter of A . For any subset S of A , let $F(S) := \bigcap \{F \in \mathfrak{F}(A) : S \subseteq F\}$. Then $F(S)$ is the smallest UP-filter of A containing S . Therefore, if S and T are UP-filters in a UP-algebra A , then $S \sqcap T := S \cap T$ and $S \sqcup T := F(S \cup T)$ are UP-filters in A . So, $(\mathfrak{F}(A), \sqcap, \sqcup)$ is a complete lattice.

2.3. Meet-commutative UP-algebras. A UP-algebra A is said to be meet-commutative (see [5], Definition 3) if it satisfies the condition

$$(2) (\forall x, y \in A)((x \cdot y) \cdot y = (y \cdot x) \cdot x).$$

However, this term also appears (Definition 1.15) in the paper [15]. We begin this subsection with the following example.

Example 2.2. Let $A = \{0, a, b\}$ and operations ‘ \cdot ’ defined on A as follows:

\cdot	0	a	b
0	0	a	b
a	0	0	a
b	0	0	0

Then $A = (A, \cdot, 0)$ is a meet-commutative UP-algebra ([15], Example 1,16).

Example 2.3. ([16], Example 2.2) Let $A = \{0, a, b, c, d, e\}$ and operations ‘ \cdot ’ defined on A as follows:

\cdot	0	a	b	c	d	e
0	0	a	b	c	d	e
a	0	0	b	c	d	e
b	0	a	0	c	d	e
c	0	a	b	0	d	e
d	0	a	b	c	0	e
e	0	a	b	c	d	0

Then $A = (A, \cdot, 0)$ is a meet-commutative UP-algebra. For example, $(a \cdot b) \cdot b = (b \cdot a) \cdot a = 0$ and $(b \cdot e) \cdot e = (e \cdot b) \cdot b = 0$.

The following example shows that any UP-algebra may not satisfy the condition (2).

Example 2.4. ([5], Example 3) Let $A = \{0, a, b, c\}$ and operations ‘ \cdot ’ defined on A as follows:

\cdot	1	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c
a	0	0	a	a
b	0	0	0	a
c	0	0	0	0

Then $A = (A, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra which does not satisfy the condition (2). For example, for $x = b$ and $y = c$, we have $(x \cdot y) \cdot y = (b \cdot c) \cdot c = a \cdot c = a$ but $(y \cdot x) \cdot x = (c \cdot b) \cdot b = 0 \cdot b = b$.

We first characterize the meet-commutative UP-algebras.

Theorem 2.1 ([8]). *Let A be a meet-commutative UP-algebra. Then the following holds*

$$(\forall x, y \in A)(x \leq y \implies y = (y \cdot x) \cdot x).$$

The following theorem is crucial for understanding this logic environment and recognizing the properties of various types of UP-filters in such an environment.

Theorem 2.2 ([8]). *Let A be a meet-commutative UP-algebra. For any $x, y \in A$, the element*

$$x \sqcup y := (x \cdot y) \cdot y = (y \cdot x) \cdot x$$

is the least upper bound of x and y .

Theorem 2.3 ([12, 13]). *Let A be a meet-commutative UP-algebra. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} & (\forall x, y \in A)(0 \sqcup x = x, x \sqcup 0 = 0, x \sqcup x = x, \text{ and } x \sqcup y = y \sqcup x). \\ & (\forall x, y, z \in A)((x \sqcup y) \sqcup z = (x \sqcup z) \sqcup (y \sqcup z)). \\ & (\forall x, y, z \in A)((z \cdot x) \sqcup (z \cdot y) \leq z \cdot (x \sqcup y)). \\ & (\forall x, y, z \in A)((x \sqcup y) \cdot z \leq (x \cdot z) \sqcup (y \cdot z)). \\ & (\forall x, y \in A)(x \sqcup y \leq (y \cdot x) \sqcup (x \cdot y)). \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.4. *If A is a meet-commutative UP-algebra, then (A, \sqcup) is the upper semilattice.*

Relying on one of the results of Theorem 2.3, we conclude that (A, \sqcup) is a semilattice with respect to the operation ' \sqcup ' with special distributivity property different than that the concept of 'distributive semilattice' described in the book [2], for example.

3. PRIME AND IRREDUCIBLE UP-FILTERS

In this and the next section, we will assume that the algebra A is a meet-commutative UP-algebra. Although the material presented in this section can be found in [8], it is included in this report due to the consistency of the entire content.

Definition 3.1. ([8]) Let F a UP-filter of A . Then F is said to be a *prime UP-filter* of A if the following holds

$$(PF) (\forall x, y \in A)(x \sqcup y \in F \implies (x \in F \vee y \in F)).$$

Example 3.2. Let $A = \{0, a, b, c\}$ and operations ' \cdot ' defined on A as follows:

\cdot	0	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c
a	0	0	0	0
b	0	c	0	c
c	0	b	b	0

Then $A = (A, \cdot, 0)$ is a meet-commutative UP-algebra. Subsets $\{0\}$, $\{0, b\}$, $\{0, c\}$ and $\{0, a, b, c\}$ are UP-filters of A . It is not difficult to verify that UP filters $\{0, b\}$ and $\{0, c\}$ are prime. It is clear that $\{0\}$ is not a prime IP-filter of A because $b \sqcup c = 0 \in \{0\}$ but $b \notin \{0\}$ and $c \notin \{0\}$.

Definition 3.3. ([8]) A UP-filter F of a A is said to be an *irreducible UP-filter* of A if for any UP-filters S and T of A the following implication holds

$$F = S \cap T \implies (S = F \vee T = F).$$

Theorem 3.1 ([8]). *Any prime UP-filter in a meet-commutative UP-algebra is an irreducible UP-filter.*

Proof. Suppose F is a prime UP-filter of a UP-algebra A . Let S and T be UP-filters of A such that $F = S \cap T$. Let us assume that the elements $a, b \in A$ be such that $a \in S$ and $b \in T$ holds. Since $a \leq a \sqcup b$ and $b \leq a \sqcup b$ holds, it follows $a \sqcup b \in S$ and $a \sqcup b \in T$ because S and T are UP-filters in UP-algebra A . Then $a \sqcup b \in S \cap T = F$. From here, it follows $a \in F$ or $b \in F$ because F is a prime UP-filter of A . Since this inclusion holds for arbitrary elements $a \in S$ and $b \in T$, we conclude that $S \subseteq F$ or $T \subseteq F$ holds. As the inverse inclusion certainly holds, we conclude that $S = F$ or $T = F$ holds. \square

Example 3.4. Let A be as in Example 2.3. The subsets $\{0\}$, $\{0, a\}$ and A are UP-filters in A . As shown in Example 2.3, it is clear that $\{0\}$ is not a prime UP-filter in A because for elements $a, b \in A$ holds $a \sqcup b \in \{0\}$ but $a \notin \{0\}$ and $b \notin \{0\}$. The only prime UP-filter in A is just A .

4. CONCEPT OF WEAKLY IRREDUCIBLE UP-FILTERS

This and the next section form a major part of this report. First, the notion of weakly irreducible UP-filter is introduced in a meet-commutative UP-algebra, and then one of its important characterizations is given and it is connected with irreducible and prime UP-filters.

Definition 4.1. Let F be a UP-filter of A . F is a *weakly irreducible UP-filter* in A if and only if for all UP-filter S and T of A such that $S \cap T \subseteq F$ the following holds $S \subseteq F$ or $T \subseteq F$.

Example 4.2. Let A be as in the example 3.2. Then A is a meet-commutative UP-algebra. For the UP filter $F := \{0, b\}$ we have $\{0, b\} \cap \{0, a, b, c\} \subseteq F$ and $\{0, b\} \subseteq F$. Thus, F is a weakly irreducible UP-filter in A .

The following theorem gives one important characterization of weakly irreducible UP-filters in meet-commutative UP-algebras.

Theorem 4.1. Let F be a UP-filter in A . Then F is weakly irreducible if and only if the following conditions hold

$$(WIrF) (\forall x, y \in A)((x \notin F \wedge y \notin F) \implies (\exists z \notin F)(x \leq z \wedge y \leq z)).$$

Proof. Assume that F is a weakly irreducible UP-filter in A and let elements $x, y \in A$ be such that $x \notin F$ and $y \notin F$. Let us design UP-filters $F_x = F(F \cup \{x\})$ and $F_y = F(F \cup \{y\})$. It is obvious that $F \subseteq F_x \cap F_y$. If it were $F = F_x \cap F_y$, we would have $x \in F_x \subseteq F$ or $y \in F_y \subseteq F$ which is impossible according to the hypothesis. So it has to be $F \subset F_x \cap F_y$. Thus, there exists an element $z \in F_x \cap F_y$ such that $z \notin F$. In addition to the above, it is obvious that $x \leq z$ and $y \leq z$ are valid.

Opposite, suppose that the UP filter F in an algebra A satisfies the condition (WIrF) and let S and T be UP filters in A such that $S \cap T \subseteq F$. Suppose now that $\neg(S \subseteq F)$ and $\neg(T \subseteq F)$ are valid. Then there exists an element $x \in S$ such that $x \notin F$ and there exists an element $y \in T$ such that $y \notin F$. By assumption, there exists a $z \notin F$ such that $x \leq z$ and $y \leq z$. On the other hand, we have $z \in S$ and $z \in T$ and by consequently $z \in S \cap T \subseteq F$ which is a contradiction. Thus, it must be $S \subseteq F$ or $T \subseteq F$ thus proving that F is a weakly irreducible UP-filter in A . \square

The following example illustrates the circumstances in the previous theorem:

Example 4.3. Let A be as in the Examples 3.2. Subset $G := \{0, c\}$ is a weakly irreducible UP-filter in A because for the elements $a, b \notin G$, the following holds $b \notin G$ and $a \leq b \wedge b \leq b$.

Theorem 4.2. Every weakly irreducible UP-filter in a meet-commutative UP-algebra is a prime UP-filter.

Proof. Let F be a weakly irreducible UP-filter in a meet-commutative UP-algebra A and let $x, y \in A$ be such that $x \sqcup y \in F$. If we assume that $x \notin F$ and $y \notin F$, then there exists an element $z \notin F$ such that $x \leq z$ and $y \leq z$. Since z is the upper bound for x and y , it must be $x \sqcup y \leq z$. Then $z \in F$. We got a contradiction. Therefore, it must be $x \in F$ or $y \in F$ which means that F is a prime UP-filter. \square

Theorem 4.3. Every weakly irreducible UP-filter of a meet-commutative UP-algebra is an irreducible UP-filter.

Proof. The proof of this theorem is directly obtained by combining Theorem 3.1 and Theorem 4.2. \square

The proof of Theorem 4.3 can be derived without reference to Theorem 4.2. Indeed:

Proof. Let F be a weakly irreducible UP-filter in A . Let S and T be UP filters in A such that $F = S \cap T$. Then $F \subseteq S$ and $F \subseteq T$. If we assume that $F \neq S$ and $F \neq T$, then there are elements $x \in S$ and $y \in T$ such that $x \notin F$ and $y \notin F$. Since F is a weakly irreducible UP-filter in A , by Theorem 4.1, there is an element $z \notin F$ with $x \leq z$ and $y \leq z$. On the other hand, we have $z \in S \cap T = F$ which is a contradiction. So, F is irreducible. \square

As shown in [8], any prime UP-filter (of the first kind) in a meet-commutative UP-algebra is an irreducible UP-filter. In this paper it is shown that the weakly irreducible UP filter is a prime UP filter (of the first kind) and, therefore, the irreducible UP filter. It is quite natural to ask the question: When will the reverse be true?

One of the answers can be recognized immediately:

Theorem 4.4. *If the lattice $\mathfrak{F}(A)$ of a meet-commutative UP-algebra A is distributive, then any irreducible UP-filter in A is a weakly irreducible UP-filter in A .*

Proof. Let F , S and T be UP-filters in a meet-commutative UP-algebra A such that $S \cap T \subseteq F$ and F be irreducible. Then

$$F = (S \cap T) \sqcup F = (S \cap T) \sqcup F = (S \sqcup F) \cap (T \sqcup F) = (S \sqcup F) \cap (T \sqcup F)$$

since $\mathfrak{F}(A)$ is a distributive lattice. As F is an irreducible UP-filter in A , it holds $S \sqcup F = F$ or $T \sqcup F = F$. This implies that $S \subseteq F$ or $T \subseteq F$. Therefore, F is a weakly irreducible UP-filter in A . \square

It is quite justified to ask the question: Is this condition necessary?

5. FINAL COMMENTS AND POSSIBLE FURTHER WORK

The algebra class called 'UP-algebra' was designed by A Iampan in [3]. This class of logical algebras has been the subject of many articles (See, for example [4, 5, 11, 15, 17]). As usual, various types of filters in this class of algebra were studied (for example, [4, 5, 11, 14]). One special subclass of these logical algebras, the class of meet-commutative UP-algebras, was introduced by Sawika et al. [15] and somewhat more information on this class of UP-algebra is given by Muhiuddin et al. in the article [8]. In addition, in the last mentioned article, the authors introduced and analyzed the concept of prime UP-filters (of the first kind) and the concept of irreducible UP-filters in meet-commutative UP-algebras. In this paper, as a continuation of previous research, the author introduces and analyzes the concept of weakly irreducible UP-filters in such UP-algebras by weakening the filter's irreducibility requirements. The author is inclined to convey his belief that this research raises a general understanding of meet-commutative algebras to other researchers of the class of UP-algebras.

One of the possible extensions of article [8] and this paper is the analysis of the possibility of introducing the concept of semi-prime UP-filters in meet-commutative UP-algebras:

Let A be a meet-commutative UP-algebra. A UP-filter F of A is said to be a *semi-prime UP-filter* of A if the following holds

$$(\forall x, y, z \in A)((x \sqcup y \in F \wedge x \sqcup z \in F) \implies (\exists d \in A)(d \leq y \wedge d \leq z)(x \sqcup d \in F)).$$

The term semi-prime ideal was first used by W. Krull in his famous paper [7] (pp. 735). (Cited according to [10], page 107.). Y. Rav adapted this term to general lattices ([10]). In addition, in the mentioned article, Rav introduced and analyzed the concept of semi-prime filters in general lattices, also. These concepts have been studied in several research papers (see, for example, [1]).

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